

Insights into Carolingian construction techniques – results from archaeological and mineralogical studies at Müstair Monastery, Grisons, Switzerland

Marta Caroselli¹, Christine Bläuer², Patrick Cassitti³, Giovanni Cavallo¹, Irka Hajdas⁴, Sophie Hueglin³, Hans Neukom³, Albert Jornet¹

(1) University of Applied Arts and Sciences of Southern Switzerland (SUPSI), Institute of Material and Construction (IMC) marta.caroselli@supsi.ch

(2) Conservation Science Consulting Sàrl, Fribourg, Switzerland.

(3) Foundation Pro Monastery of St. John, Müstair, Switzerland.

(4) Laboratory of Ion Beam Physics, ETH, Zurich, Switzerland

Abstract

During decades of archaeological investigations at the monastery of St. John in Müstair, a World Heritage site located in the canton of Grisons, Switzerland, more than 5000 mortar samples dated between about AD 775 and AD 1800 have been recovered. The site also features the remains of five mechanical mortar mixers dating from the 8th to the 10th century. This monastery acts as a case study to recount materials and methods in medieval and early modern construction sites. The proposed paper will focus on the earliest construction phase, which has been dated by dendrochronology between AD 775 and 788. A large number of archaeological features can be attributed to the Carolingian construction site: trenches, post-holes, fills, deposits of lime and plaster, as well as imprints on soil and mortar. They offer insights into the organization of the building site and the progression of the work. The petrographic analyses of mortars and raw materials further complement and expand our knowledge of Carolingian building techniques, so that different mortar groups have been identified with different petrographic characteristics.

1. Introduction

Building technology in general and mortar production in particular have been identified as key elements to understand and scientifically date materials, methods, movements and motivations of builders and patrons, especially for periods and sites with little evidence to draw on [1]. Building materials reflect natural resources as well as cultural choices. Methods of preparation and construction vary with period and purpose, but can tell also of skills and working conditions. With the movement of men, animals and materials also technologies and ideas are transported and create connections between sites far apart.

The above-mentioned aspects of the history of construction are being studied as part of the project "Mortar technology and construction history at Müstair Monastery".⁸ The focus of the project lies on the study of mortar fragments from the UNESCO World Heritage site of the Monastery of St John at Müstair. The monastery is amongst the best preserved monastic sites in Europe and since 1969 has been systematically investigated archaeologically below ground [2]. It is exceptionally well suited to a study of the development of stone building technology because it has a history of almost continuous construction activity for over a thousand years.

Moreover, the monastery boasts about 5000 samples of mortar from all periods, which allows us to correlate certain mortar types with period and function, as well as specific preparation and application methods. The importance of the study of mortars concerns their technical process of production. The scientific study of the material has implications in historical, archaeological and technological contexts [3].

The aims of this paper are: i) to study the mortar of all the buildings attributed to the Carolingian phase (church, convent, loggia building and Holy Cross Chapel); ii) to study the archaeological documentation of the excavation to identify particular construction techniques of the Carolingian phase; iii) to understand whether there are any similarities or differences (type of binder, type of aggregate, texture) in mortars with different functions: bedding mortar, floor mortar, plaster, painted plaster; iv) to extend our knowledge about the relationship between the archaeological findings and the results of the analytical studies of building materials.

Situation of the monastery in the Carolingian period

The Monastery of Müstair has been a very important religious, political and economic centre for many centuries. The largest surviving fresco paintings cycle of Carolingian Europe dated to the early 9th century, which decorates the church of St. John the Baptist, is evidence of its importance at the time of Charlemagne [4].

The monastery has been excavated almost in its entirety. The general chronological sequence is well understood in its main phases. Since then, as research at the site has progressed, our knowledge of the history and architectural development of the monastery has increased and some of the originally proposed dates have been corrected or further refined [5].

Dated to the year 775 by dendrochronology, the abbey church is one of only two surviving Carolingian churches in Switzerland. Archaeological investigations have established that the church was the first part of the monastery to be built [6]. The Carolingian complex consisted of a large, regular, two storeyed quadrilateral structure, with a large central courtyard

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surrounded on all four sides by open corridors and convent buildings, here called north, east, south and west wing respectively [2]. After the completion of the monastery, several additions and changes were made to the buildings. These additions have been subsumed under the term “second Carolingian construction phase”. Therefore, in the Carolingian period, buildings can be attributed to one of two phases: Phase I comprises the abbey church, the convent buildings and the Holy Cross-chapel, and dates between 774 and 788; phase II mainly describes an internal addition to the convent south corridor (the so-called “loggia building”) as well as water basins and cellars in the same courtyard. These additions were constructed at some time between the late 8th and the early 10th century (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Reconstruction plan of the monastery during the Carolingian phases I and II [7, modified]. Main Church, convent (with corridors and wings around an open courtyard) and Holy Cross Chapel of phase I are coloured dark blue, the “loggia building” and other phase II buildings are light blue. Red dots represent the position of the mortar samples.

The monastery of St. John is one of the oldest examples of a church with cloister in Europe [8]. Its size is comparable to the largest monasteries of the time, such as the Reichenau [9] or San Vincenzo al Volturno [10]. This oldest part of the monumental complex with its two Carolingian phases was followed by at least eight major construction phases across 1200 years, which demonstrate the continuing importance of the site.

2. Material and methods

2.1 Archaeological research

Uniquely, at the monastery of St. John, conservation work has gone hand in hand with scientific research both above and below ground since 1969. The results led to a new understanding of the history and structural development of the monastery. Müstair monastery was one of the first archaeological sites in Central Europe, where the study of the remnants above as well as below ground was carried out. The stratigraphic study of the layers of soil and other characteristics was accompanied by a meticulous study of the walls and other features, which were still standing above ground. The archaeological layers could

thus be paralleled with extant structures. Since many of the monastery buildings can be precisely dated through dendrochronology, most archaeological features below ground are also chronologically well understood.

At present, only a small part of the archaeological results has been published. Most of it still awaits detailed evaluation. As part of the present project, the documentation regarding the construction layers which can be attributed to the various building phases of the monastery is being evaluated in detail. The investigation into the archaeological layers and features which can be attributed to the construction of the Carolingian convent has been completed only recently. They provide important insights into the organization of the building site for the Carolingian construction.

2.2 Selection of Carolingian fragments

In order to better understand the construction sequence and techniques of the two Carolingian construction phases, 120 mortar fragments attributed by archaeologists to these two first phases, have been chosen for characterization and comparison. Close attention was paid to the selection of samples from all major buildings and – when possible – only from primary (in situ) contexts. Sometimes, in the case of very long walls, it was necessary to take several samples. Furthermore, the samples cover different mortar types, the major categories being: bedding mortars, plasters and painted plasters (Table 1). Currently the floor mortars and the mortar from mortar mixers have not yet been analysed. In many cases the plasters were found to be composed of different layers: when present, we called *arriccio* the ground layer with coarse aggregate and *intonaco* the one beneath the painted layer and with finer aggregate.

Table 1: Carolingian samples selected and analysed. The table indicates the description of the source area (Figure 1), the sample ID, the mortar function and the research question connected with the sample.

Source area	Sample(s)	Mortar function	Research question
Church	23288, 23289, 6577, 11902	Bedding mortar	Common characteristics?
Church	11970	Bedding mortar	Compare with 8589 and 11902
Church Carolingian?	15439	Bedding mortar	Carolingian phase II?
Church	15783	Bedding mortar	Mud lime mortar?
Church	25005, 8589, 12593	Plaster	Similar to other Carolingian inside plasters of church or convent?
Church	24150-1B, 24150-3, 24150-4B, 24150-19, 24150-20	Painted plaster	Similar to other painted plaster from church?
Carolingian W-wing E-wall/W-corridor W-	957	Bedding mortar	Similar to other bedding mortars Carolingian phase I NESW-wings and -corridors?

Source area	Sample(s)	Mortar function	Research question
Carolingian N-wing N-wall N001	5410	Bedding mortar	Similar to other bedding mortars Carolingian phase I NESW-wings and -corridors?
Carolingian phase II NE	8154	Bedding mortar	Compare with 8647 from same well
Carolingian N- corridor S-wall foundation zone	8700	Bedding mortar	Similar to all bedding mortars Carolingian NESW-wings and - corridors, e.g. 9096 and 10637?
Carolingian N- corridor S-wall	10637	Bedding mortar (Sample with two different mortar varieties)	Similar to other bedding mortars of Carolingian NESW-wings and - corridors, e.g. 8700) and 9096
Carolingian outbuilding S-wall	3219	Bedding mortar	Similar to Carolingian outbuilding E-wall?
Carolingian S- corridor N-wall E- part	3769	Bedding mortar (with brick fragments)	Similar to other bedding mortars of Carolingian NESW-wings and – corridors, e.g. 3136?
Carolingian S-wing internal N-S-wall	12480	Bedding mortar	Similar to 12780 and to 12781?
Carolingian phase II Carolingian S-wing internal N-S-wall	12610	Bedding mortar	Compare with bedding mortar and plaster from Loggia building
Carolingian S-wing internal N-S-wall	12781	Bedding mortar	Compare with 12480 and 12780
Carolingian E-wing E-wall	14480	Bedding mortar	Compare with bedding mortars Carolingian phase I Carolingian NESW-wings and –corridors
Carolingian E- corridor E- wall/Carolingian E- wing W-wall	14977	Bedding mortar	Compare with bedding mortars Carolingian phase I Carolingian NESW-wings and –corridors.
W-wing (remains of) fireplace (open chimney) adjacent to E-wall W-front	315	Bedding mortar (in context with fireplace)	Different from bedding mortar 957 and from 494 floor mortar from underneath fireplace?
E-corridor W-wall E- front	12941	Mud-lime plaster	Similar to 13015?
N-corridor S-wall N- front	10402	Plaster	Similar to other bedding mortars Carolingian NESW-wings and - corridors, e.g. 9096 and 10637?
Doorway in Carolingian S- corridor S-wall	13023	Plaster	Similar to 3137, 3676 and 13018?
Carolingian S- corridor N-wall W- part	3136	Bedding mortar	Similar to other bedding mortars Carolingian NESW-wings and - corridors?
Loggia building	10127, 1260	Bedding mortar	Similar to bedding mortar 10126 from cellar 718 and 10134 from loggia building?

Source area	Sample(s)	Mortar function	Research question
Carolingian S-corridor N-wall	3137, 3676	Plaster	Similar to other bedding mortars Carolingian NESW-wings and -corridors, e.g. 3676?
Loggia building	9105-4B	Painted plaster	Difference to painted plasters from Carolingian phase I? Similar to other samples from 9105, 12180 and 12855?
Holy Cross Chapel	24965, 24966	Bedding mortar	Reference layer, compare to plaster 24608
Holy Cross Chapel	24967, 24969, 24972	Bedding mortar	Compare to other bedding mortars
Holy Cross Chapel	24608, 24970, 24979, 24980, 24609, 24978, 24650	Plaster	Compare to other plasters
Holy Cross Chapel	13/15;LIII1.02, 13/16;AEIII1.02	Plaster	Reference layer, compare to other plasters

2.3 Analytical studies of mortars

The mortar samples were first described using a binocular lens allowing up to 70x magnification. This description recorded the following features: a) binder colour and structure; b) the presence or not of lime lumps and their size; c) the overall colour, grain size and shape of the aggregate and the maximum grain size; d) the presence of additions like fibres, charcoal, brick, etc.; e) the macroscopically visible porosity and finally e) some notion on the overall hardness of the mortar and an estimation of the binder to aggregate ratio.

After this first selection, from 52 samples (listed in Table 1) thin polished petrographic sections were prepared by a specialized laboratory. On these, the following features were observed by means of polarized light microscopy [11]: binder: structure, colour, birefringence, homogeneity; lime lump types, e.g. internal structures, and their size; aggregate grains: grain sizes, grain shapes, mineral and rock types present; estimation of the grain size distribution and minimal and maximal grain sizes; additions and special features like e.g. brick grains or grains of partly melted binder material, etc.; macro-porosity: like retraction fissures, air pockets and water voids.

The thin sections of the mortars from the Holy Cross Chapel have been analysed by point counting [12]. The binder to aggregate ratio (B/A) was calculated to represent the volumes of the dolomitic lime putty versus the volume of sand, as it was mixed in the initial recipe. It was considered that the binder volume used as a putty neither expanded nor shrank much during setting, hence that the volume of the binder determined by point counting represents approximately the volume of the lime putty used. The volume of sand used for mixing a mortar is measured as numbers of shovels or buckets, hence this volume does contain, apart

from rock fragments, grains, i.e. the actual sand grains, also the voids in between them. In an average sand the voids make up about 45% of the total volume and only 55% of the volume are the sand grains. By point counting however only the rock fragments can be counted, hence the value determined for the aggregate only represents 55% of the actual volume of sand used initially. For the B/A ratios reported here, the point counted volumes of aggregate were therefore multiplied by 1.82.

Particles of the separated mortar binders have been systematically analysed by Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy [13]. The equipment used was a Bruker ALPHA-P; preparation technique: Diamond ATR; measuring range: 4000 - 375 cm⁻¹, number of scans 24, resolution 4 cm⁻¹. The detection limit for a mineral phase in a mixture is around 2% by weight.

3. Results

3.1 Archaeological findings

The study of the archaeological remains allowed to understand the construction procedures followed at the monastery building site. First, the ground was prepared. The excavations showed that strata dated to the centuries before the Carolingian building activities are completely missing in the entire area of the Carolingian convent buildings. This came as a surprise because such strata could clearly be identified in the excavations in the later west courtyard of the monastery [14]. It is very unlikely that this is based on natural causes. It rather indicates that this is the result of flattening the ground in the entire construction area by the Carolingian workmen. However, the site was not entirely levelled into a horizontal plane, but rather left with a slight southward slope which followed the natural topography of the terrain.

The reason for leaving the site with a slight slope might be seen in the fact that the amount of material that had to be removed was considerably less than if the whole site had been completely levelled to a horizontal plane. Furthermore, water was naturally drained from the site during heavy rain and therefore prevented the site from being waterlogged. The construction work proper took place on the surface which had thus been obtained. These activities resulted in the deposition of layers containing charcoal, mortar and lime as well as fine chippings of stone, marble and brick.

After the construction area had been prepared, the position of the foundation trenches was laid out on the ground. The southern wing of the convent is the only place where foundation trenches were found that were misplaced (by about 1 m to the north) and filled in again, before the proper foundation trenches were dug. The foundation trenches were dug through 60 to 100 cm of underlying clay down to natural soil in order to find stable ground to support the massive walls of the two storied convent buildings [15].

The Carolingian foundations were constructed with two different layers. The bottom layer was built with two courses of rounded stones bound with clay which filled the foundation trench completely. The top layer was then built with one or several courses of stones bound with mortar on which then the wall proper was built [15].

The impressions of small square wooden pegs in the mortar of the foundations were found in the inner corners of the rooms. The impressions show that the pegs were sitting on the bottom course of the foundation stones. They probably served to hold strings that marked the planned location of the inner sides of the walls. This would have allowed a greater precision when erecting the walls on top of the more irregular foundations. No such impressions, however, were found on the outer side of walls which means that the thickness was probably determined by using measuring rods.

The remains of a Carolingian mortar mixer lie north of abbey church and convent. The pit of the mixer is ca. 3.20 -3.40 m in diameter and at least 40 cm deep; in the middle of the pit is a posthole filled with vertical stones which used to hold a now lost wooden post, originally acting as pivot for the rotating part of the device.

Several features show the importance of water on the construction site. Water channels crossed the construction site, and were filled in after the completion of the building.

After the construction was complete, the surface was flattened again by spreading a layer of soil which covered all the features related to the building of the monastery. On top of this layer of soil the mortar floors and ovens of the monastery were then constructed.

3.2 Characterization of mortars

Abbey Church. The petrographic analyses of the bedding mortars from the abbey church show common characteristics: rich in binder ($B/A > 1$), the grain size of the sand varies from medium to coarse (up to 8 mm), and is not well sorted (Figure 2A). The peculiarity of the aggregate composition is the absence of carbonate phases. The only one that contains dolomite fragments is sample 11902 taken at a height of 2.85 m in the facade. The pores are roundish and/or irregular in shape. The observation of thin sections of plasters allowed to discriminate 5 layers: 1) external painted layer, 2) whitewash layer; 3) *intonaco* with a well-sorted sand of fine grain size from silica metamorphic rocks (carbonate also present); 4) whitewash layer; 5) The *arriccio* is made of unsorted sand of coarse grain size up to 1 cm, from metamorphic rocks and some fragments of different carbonates (Figure 2B).

Figure 2: thin section images 5x, XPOL: A) Sample 23288, bedding mortar from the main church with $B/A > 1$, aggregate without carbonates and grain size from medium to coarse. B) Sample 24150-19: layers of plaster: 3-intonaco with a well sorted sand of fine grain size; 4- whitewash layer; 5- *arriccio* with unsorted sand of coarse grain size.

Convent. The bedding mortars collected from the convent were much poorer in binder (B/A 1:1). They also differ from the mortars from the church in the aggregate because here the finer grain size is also present together with medium and coarse sands (up to 1 cm). The aggregate also contains carbonate rock fragments (Figure 3A). The plasters are characterized by a high amount of binder when compared with the bedding mortars from the same areas. The plasters consist of a single layer of *arriccio* made of unsorted sand with a grain size from fine to coarse. The aggregate is mainly composed of fragments from metamorphic rocks (gneiss, schist), quartz in single crystals, dolomite, limestone and micas (Figure 3B).

Figure 3: thin section images 5x, XPOL. A) Sample 12781, bedding mortar from the convent. An unsorted sand with carbonate phases is visible. B) Sample 315, the plaster consists of a single layer of *arriccio* covered by a whitewash layer.

Loggia building. The bedding mortars of the “loggia building” and the convent are very similar: even if a higher presence of micas seems to be present in mortars from the former (Figure 4A). The painted plaster of all the fragments of the “loggia building” is characterised by a light brown colour due to high presence of very fine crystals of (possible) clay minerals that gives it its strong yellowish colour. The painted plaster consists of a single layer of *arriccio* with Mg-lime binder and a not sorted sand. The aggregate is mainly composed of

fragments from metamorphic rocks (gneiss, schist), quartz in single crystals and micas. In these painted plasters there are no carbonate rock fragments in the sand (Figure 4B).

Figure 4: thin section images 5x, XPOL. A) Sample 10127 bedding mortar of the “loggia building” similar to those of the convent; B) sample 9105, painted plaster of the loggia building characterized by high presence of very fine crystals of (possible) clay minerals.

Holy Cross Chapel. The analysis shows that the intonaci of the Chapel of the Holy Cross are very rich (Figure 5) in binder: binder to aggregate ratios near between 1:0.5 (3 samples) and 1:1.5 (one sample) volume ratios. All but one bedding mortar and all plasters and the analysed arriccio were much poorer in binder showing binder to aggregate ratios of 1: 2 to 1:3.5.

Figure 5: Thin section from *intonaco* of the Holy Cross Chapel, with a high B/A and mainly crystalline rock fragments as aggregate. Sample 24980: Left PPol, right XPOL.

The maximal grain size of the aggregate is 2 mm for all intonaci except one where grains up to 4 mm could be observed. This sample is the same, showing a less binder-rich mixture than the others. The bedding mortars do contain sand grains of up to 10 mm in size and probably even larger (only small samples of maximally a few cm in diameter were available for the laboratory analysis). An exception from this is the bedding mortar from the choir screen and one from the north wall of the nave, which both show a maximum grain size of only 2 mm.

All aggregates in the mortars are mixtures of carbonates, usually dolomites, and carbonate-free rocks, with the carbonate-free rock fragments being much more abundant. The carbonate fragment content of the 15 samples analysed lie between 3% and just below 20%

by volume of the total aggregate. Further investigations will show whether this observation can be correlated with specific proveniences of the sands. The majority of the aggregates of the mortars from the Holy Cross Chapel are rock fragments rich in quartz, feldspar and muscovite (Figure 5). More rarely rock fragments containing biotite or two mica gneisses can be found. Accessorily rock fragments containing minerals like black or blue tourmaline, amphiboles, epidotes or rutile can be found.

Figure 6: Siliceous, melted phases in a plaster (intonaco) of the Holy Cross Chapel, Scale bar 50 μ m. Sample 24'978. Left PPOL, right XPOL

The binder in all samples consists exclusively of dolomitic lime and in most samples some siliceous phases belonging to the binder could be observed either through microscopy (Figure 6) or in the FTIR spectra. The mineralogy determined through FTIR spectroscopy showed that the binders of all Carolingian samples contained calcite as well as dolomitic lime-related phases, usually magnesite or hydromagnesite (Figure 7). In one plaster sample some residual brucite ($Mg(OH)_2$) was analysed, in five samples the presence of aragonite could be assumed.

Figure 7: FTIR spectrum of the sample 24972. Peaks of calcite are: 1796, (peak at around 1396 cm^{-1} is covered by carbonate double peaks of hydromagnesite), 873, 712 cm^{-1} . Peaks identifying hydromagnesite are: 3648, 3506, 3443, shoulder at 1473, 1415, 854, 794, 744, 590 cm^{-1} .

4. Discussion

The binder of all the mortar and plaster samples from the monastery analysed so far is made from dolomitic lime and it can be assumed that they have been produced from local dolomitic rocks, as the geology of the valley of Müstair is strongly dominated by dolomites but limestones are very rare [16]. Which dolomite was used in which period to produce the binder materials for the mortars is at the moment under investigation as part of the same research project: preliminary results are reported in another paper in this volume [17].

Two different groups of bedding mortar have been identified with different petrographic characteristics: one comes from the main church and one from the large adjacent building complex to the west, which consists of the convent, the “loggia building” and the Holy Cross Chapel.

The mortars and plasters of the church are very rich in binder and the plasters are characterized by four layers as preparation of the surfaces to be painted. This indicates execution by specialized workers and a very accurate realization for the most important building of the monumental complex. The interposition of the whitewash between the *arriccio* and the *intonaco* probably means that the church was not decorated at first, confirming more recent archaeological hypotheses [18]. Sample 11902, the only one that contains dolomite fragments, was taken from a heavily disturbed part of the wall, into which windows were inserted in the 15th and 18th century. It could therefore belong to a later phase.

The archaeological investigations have shown that the church was completed before work on the cloister started. This is shown by the fact that the walls of the church do not interlock with those of the convent. This, together with the fact that there are clear differences between the mortars used in the construction of the church and those used for the convent, seems to indicate that two different workshops were involved in the construction of the monastery. Considering that the church is architecturally more complex than the rest of the monastery, with higher walls, five apses and two annexes, this result could indicate that specialists were called for its construction, while the convent was constructed by another workshop.

There are marked differences between the plasters in the different Carolingian buildings. Like those in the church, the pictorial surfaces of Holy Cross Chapel consist of several layers, *arriccio* and *intonaco*, both rich in binder. On the contrary the painted plaster fragments recovered from the convent, which stem from the Carolingian convent and the “loggia building”, consisted of a single layer. In some cases, a layer of whitewash was applied before the surface was painted, probably to homogenize the surface and make it smoother. The plaster of the “loggia building” is peculiar, as it contains a substantial fraction of clay minerals that may indicate the use of unwashed sand. From all plaster samples of the Carolingian monastery, only the plaster samples from the loggia building contain such very

fine aggregates. This choice could have been made on purpose, to take advantage of the better workability or to obtain a smoother surface due to the presence of the clayey fraction. On the other hand, the use of unwashed sand could have been fortuitous, due to an accidental change of the raw material.

Based on these observations, different groupings of the analysed plasters can be proposed, based on different characteristics. If grouped according to the number of layers of plaster, the church and the Holy Cross chapel show clear similarities, as in both buildings the interior surfaces possess an *arriccio* and an *intonaco* layer, on which the painting was applied. The painted layer from the convent, on the other hand, has been applied directly onto the first layer of plaster after it was covered with a layer of whitewash. If grouped according to the characteristics of the plaster, then the fragments belonging to the “loggia building” stand out because of the presence of a clayey fraction. It seems that a clear distinction exists between the painted plasters from the two religious buildings and from the convent buildings. This could be due to a difference in status or in function of the decorated interiors. Possibly they also indicate the work of different groups of people. The very peculiar character of the plaster from the “loggia building” sets it apart from all the others. As it is the youngest Carolingian building, which was added sometime after the work on the monastery had been completed, this difference might be due to yet another group of craftsmen being in charge of the interior decoration.

From their mineralogical composition, it can be assumed that the sands used as aggregates for the diverse mortars came from a local source. The exact provenience of the sand is still under investigation as part of this project, but different supply sources for sands can be assumed: the mortars of the church and the plaster of the “loggia building” do not have a carbonate fraction, unlike all the other samples. This characteristic is typical of the sands of the north-eastern side of the Val Müstair, while the main watercourse which runs through the valley, the river Rom, carries sands with important carbonate fractions. The use of sand collected from different areas could be a further proof of the non-contemporaneity of the construction of these buildings.

5. Conclusion

This preliminary report of an interdisciplinary project shows the contribution that each individual discipline can provide. Only by combining the results of all research areas can an almost complete picture be drawn of how construction works were done in historic times at Müstair monastery. In particular, the use of different techniques and materials (B/A ratio, sand composition, significant presence of clay minerals) found in the different buildings (church, Holy Cross Chapel, convent and “loggia building”) could indicate consecutive construction phases of the monastery, the presence of more than one team of builders, or different construction techniques chosen on purpose to differentiate between buildings with different functions and status. The usefulness of the approach followed by the project is shown by the fact that the observations from the petrographic study of the Carolingian

mortar fragments and the results of the archaeological investigations into the Carolingian construction phases so far fit very well, and do therefore complement and validate each other.

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